

THE USE OF AI IN BUSINESSES IN EUROPE

In 2021, on average 6.74% of companies in DESI countries implemented it

The DESI Index calculates the value of the “Artificial Intelligence” variable which is defined as the percentage of companies that use at least two artificial intelligence technologies. The data refer to the period between 2014 and 2021.

Ranking of European countries by artificial intelligence value in 2021. The Czech Republic and Malta are in first place for the value of artificial intelligence in 2021 with a value of 10.60, followed by Austria with a value of 9.78 and Greece with an amount of 9.03. In the middle of the table are Germany with a value of 7.37, Belgium with an amount of 6.41 and Spain with a value of 5.98. Cyprus closes the ranking with a value of 3.96, Ireland with a value of 3.76, and Slovakia with an amount equal to 3.66. Overall, the average value of AI use was 6.74 in DESI countries in 2021.

Ranking of DESI countries by absolute variation of Artificial Intelligence between 2014 and 2021. The Czech Republic and Malta are in first place with a value of the absolute variation of artificial intelligence equal to an amount of 4.78, followed by Austria with a value of 4.41 and from Greece with a value of 4.08 units. In the middle of the table are Belgium with a value of 2.89, the Netherlands with a value of 2.84, and Spain with a value of 2.70 units. Cyprus closed the ranking with a value of 1.79, Ireland with a value of 1.70 units and Slovakia with a value of -4.59%. Overall, the average value of the absolute change in the use of AI is equal to an amount of 2.78 units.

Clustering using the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow model is presented below. The Elbow method shows the presence of a model of clusters equal to 4. From the point of view of the median of the clusters it results that the value of cluster 4-C4 is equal to an amount of 10.6 units, while the value of Cluster 1 -C1 is equal to an amount of 8.37 units, and the value of Cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 5.3 and the value of Cluster 3-C3 is equal to an amount of 3.66. It follows therefore that the following ordering: $C4 = 10.6 > C1 = 8.37 > C2 = 5.3 > C3 = 3.66$. From a geographical point of view, the presence of a dominance of Austria and the Czech Republic and the countries of Central Europe is evident compared to the countries of Eastern Europe.

Machine Learning and predictions. A predictive machine learning analysis is carried out below using ten different algorithms. The algorithms have been tested in their performance based on the reduction of statistical errors and the maximization of R2. The value of the learning rate of the algorithms is equal to 80%. To determine the best performing algorithm, 4 rankings were made each for the 4 statistical indicators used, namely MSE, RMSE, R2, and MAE. Each algorithm has been assigned a ranking. The rankings of the algorithms in the various rankings have been added up. The lowest payoff algorithms are the highest in the rankings. Therefore, the following ranking of the algorithms by predictive capacity derives:

- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 5;
- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 9;
- SGD with a payoff value of 13;
- kNN with a payoff value of 17;

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- Random Forest with a payoff value of 19;
- SVM with a payoff value of 24;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Tree with a payoff value of 29;
- Constant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

Therefore, the best algorithm for making the prediction is AdaBoost. Through the application of the AdaBoost algorithm it is possible to obtain predictions relating to the change in the investment of European companies in AI. It should be considered that the results of the prediction have been divided into three groups or winners countries, for which the growth of investment in AI is predicted, losers countries for which this trend is substantially declining and countries for which investment in AI is predicted unchanged from 2021.

The AdaBoost algorithm predicts that for the following countries there will be a growth in investment in AI:

- Slovakia with an increase from an amount of 3.66 up to a value of 4.41 or a change equal to an amount of 0.75 units equal to a value of 20.51%;
- Germany with an increase from an amount of 7.37 units up to a value of 7.95 units or a change equal to an amount of 0.58 units equivalent to approximately 7.83%;
- Hungary with an increase from an amount of 4.41 units up to a value of 4.71 units or a change equal to an amount of 0.3 units equal to a value of 6.7%;
- Ireland with an increase from an amount of 3.76 units up to a value of 3.96 units or a change equal to an amount of 0.2 units equivalent to a value of 5.25%;
- France with an increase from an amount of 5.190 up to a value of 5.4 units or equal to a change of 0.22 units equal to an amount of 4.15%;
- Sweden with an increase from an amount of 7.95 up to a value of 8.25 units or equal to a change of 0.3 units equal to an amount of 3.73%;
- Slovenia with a variation from an amount of 8.7 units up to a value of 8.97 units or a variation of 0.27 units equal to an amount of 3.1%;
- Italy with a variation from an amount of 4.71 units up to a value of 4.82 units or equal to a variation of 0.11 units equal to a variation of 2.41%;
- Finland with a variation from an amount of 5.4 units up to a value of 5.5 units or equal to an amount of 0.1 units equivalent to a variation of 1.81%;
- the Netherlands with a change to an amount of 6.3 units up to a value of 6.41 units or equal to a change of 0.11 units equal to an amount of 1.8%;
- Cyprus with a variation from an amount of 3.96 units up to a variation of 3.99 units or equal to a variation of 0.03 units or equal to an amount of 0.81%;
- Romania with a variation from an amount of 8.25 units up to a value of 8.31 units or equal to a variation of 0.06 units equal to an amount of 0.78%;
- Lithuania with a variation from an amount of 8.97 units up to a value of 9.03 units or equal to a variation of 0.06 units equal to an amount of 0.67%;
- Portugal with an increase from an amount of 8.37 units up to a value of 8.41 units or equal to a variation of 0.04 units equal to an amount of 0.48%.
- There are also two countries namely the Czech Republic and Malta for which the algorithm has predicted a variation of 0.

And finally, there are "losers" countries or countries for which the AdaBoost algorithm has predicted a reduction in investment in AI, namely:

- Luxembourg with a change to an amount of 8.41 units up to a value of 8.37 units or a change of -0.04 units equal to a value of -0.47%;
- Bulgaria with a decrease from an amount of 8.31 units up to a value of 8.25 units or equal to a variation of -0.06 units equal to a variation of -0.78%;
- Estonia with a decrease from an amount of 3.99 units up to a value of 3.96 units or equal to a variation of -0.03 units equal to a variation of -0.81%;
- Belgium with a variation from an amount of 6.41 units up to a value of 6.3 units or equal to a variation of -0.11 units equal to an amount of -1.77%.
- Spain with a variation from an amount of 5.98 units up to a value of 5.88 units or equal to a variation of -0.11 units or equal to an amount of -1.78%;
- Croatia with a variation from an amount of 5.5 units up to a value of 5.4 units or equal to a variation of -0.1 units equal to an amount of -1.79%;
- Poland with a decrease from an amount of 4.71 units up to a value of -0.11 units equal to a value of -2.35%;
- Latvia with a variation from an amount of 5.65 units up to a value of 5.5 units or equal to a variation of -0.15 units equal to an amount of -2.68%;
- Greece with a variation from an amount of 9.03 units up to a value of 8.7 units or equal to an amount of -0.33 units equal to an amount of -3.65%;
- Austria with a variation from an amount of 9.78 units up to a value of 8.97 units or equal to a variation of -0.81 units up to a value of -8.24%.

Overall, the value of the use of AI for business purposes increased from an amount of 6.74 to a value of 6.79 or equal to a variation of 0.05 units equal to an amount of 1.39 on average for the countries considered.

Conclusions. Overall, in 2021 the value of the use of AI for business purposes is reduced, or on average equal to 6.74. It follows that companies have difficulties in using artificial intelligence tools in carrying out business activities. The limits to the use of AI are the lack of corporate culture, the lack of digital culture, and the absence of adequate economic incentive policies that can facilitate companies in investing in AI. Most businesses in Europe are SMEs. SMEs show reluctance in using AI in production and business management activities.

Declarations

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